

Short communication

GLP-1RA for glycaemic control and obesity as add on therapy for type 2 diabetes

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Received: 15-04-2023, **Revised:** 10-05-2023, **Accepted:** 15-05-2023, **Published:** preprint

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HOW TO CITE THIS

Elmiladi SA (2023) GLP-1RA for glycaemic control and obesity as add on therapy for type 2 diabetes. *Mediterr J Pharm Pharm Sci.* 3 (2): 45-50. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.0000000>.

Keywords: BMI, diabetes, diabetes, GLP-1RAs, Libya, obesity

Abstract: Diabetes mellitus (DM) is a complex and chronic illness requiring continuous medical care. Type 2 diabetes (T2D) is commonly associated with obesity, hypertension, and a tendency to develop thrombosis, and increase risk of cardiovascular diseases (CVD). Diabetes is a term used to indicate an coexistence of obesity and DM. Diabetes increases as obesity is an emerging epidemic of modern societies, the co-incidence with DM is also rising, so a joint plan of anti-obesity and anti-hyperglycemia for the management approaches. Therefore, this study aimed to identify the impact of glucagon-like peptide-1 receptor agonists (GLP-1RAs) on bodyweight and glycemic response in obese Libyan patients with T2D at the National Diabetes Centre in Tripoli, between July 2013 and May 2022. This prospective study included obese adults with T2D who were newly prescribed GLP-1RA therapy for six months with dulaglutide once weekly or liraglutide once daily. The study included 170 diabetic patients were started on GLP1-RA as add on therapy to their treatment, with a regular follow up with dietitian and their physicians to adjusted their glucose lowering medications, than comparing the effect of these agents on bodyweight and the level of glycated hemoglobin before and after 24 weeks of treatment. Most of the patients (n = 99, 58.23%) were in the age period from 54 to 74 years old and 101 of whom were female subjects (59.4%), with a mean duration of DM equal to 8.8 ± 7.3 years. The patients were divided randomly into two groups, the first group included 110 patients who received liraglutide pens showed a significantly reduction in HbA1c from 9.6% (± 1.54) to 7.4% (± 1.03) by $p < 0.001$ and a significantly weight loss from 88.3 kg (± 10.68) to 80.8 kg (± 11.83) by $p < 0.001$. The reported adverse events were in 23 cases of minor hypoglycemia due to gastrointestinal upset. The other group included 60 patients for dulaglutide pens showed a significant decrease in HbA1c = 9.6% (± 1.54) to 7.1% (± 1.2) by $p < 0.05$ and a significant reduction of bodyweight from 88.3 kg (± 10.68) to 83.8 kg (± 16.3) by $p < 0.05$. The reported adverse events were mild transient gastrointestinal distressed for initial week of start than subside with regular intake. Whereas, 115 patients (67.6%) with HbA1c above 10.0% before start therapy, no patient with HbA1c above 10.0% after six months of both GLP-RA agents therapy. Thus, uses of GLP-RA as add on therapy for obese patients with T2D significantly improved the glycaemic control with less hypoglycaemia, accordingly, reduce insulin requirement for the blood glucose control and loss in bodyweight. It can thus be concluded that GLP-1RA therapy is an effective treatment option when used in the obese patients with DM.

Introduction

Worldwide, obesity is a chronic, complex, relapsing metabolic disease that affecting adults and children [1]. It is an emerging epidemic of the modern societies [1]. Nowadays, it is the major global chronic health issue according to the WHO, as it is emergent as a more serious world health problem than malnutrition [1]. By the year 2030, 60.0% of the world's population will be overweight or obese [2]. Overweight and obesity are defined as an abnormal or excessive fat accumulation that may harm health, and it is recognized to be the major risk factor for a number of non-communicable diseases, noteworthy, type 2 diabetes (T2M, account for about 45.0% of the cases), cardiovascular diseases (23.0%, CVD) which were the leading cause of death, musculoskeletal disorders as osteoarthritis: a highly disabling degenerative disease of the joints, and some cancers (07.0% - 41.0%). In addition, it reasons of many psychological problems or physical disabilities [1]. Of these diseases, T2M is utmost strongly linked with obesity (diabesity) and the frequency of obesity-related DM is projected to double to 300 million by 2025 [3]. Both, they rise the patients' mortality risk 7-fold [4]. Body mass index (BMI) is a simple index of weight for height that is commonly used to classify overweight and obesity in adults. It is defined as a person's weight in kilograms divided by the square of his height in meters. It provides the most useful population-level measure of overweight and obesity as it is the same for both sexes and for all the ages of adult. It is used to categorize overweight and obesity as BMI under 18.5 = underweight, BMI = 18.5 to < 25 = healthy, BMI = 25 to < 30 = overweight. In addition, BMI = 30 to < 35 = obese (class 1), BMI = 35 to < 40 = obese (class 2), BMI = 40 or higher = obese (class 3 - morbid). Obesity rates vary significantly from country to other as a result of different lifestyle and diet. The highest rate was reported in Nauru (61.0%) of obese adult, in the United States is found to be 36.2%, highest rate in Arabic countries is found in Kuwait (37.0%), in Jordan (35.5%), in Saudi Arabia (35.4%), in Libya (32.5%), in Egypt (32.0%), in Tunis (26.9%) and the lowest rate is in Vietnam (02.1%) [5]. Weight reduction can be attained through various plans,

involving lifestyle intervention (diet and physical exercise), pharmacotherapy, or bariatric surgery, not all of these strategies are appropriate for the patients, therefore, an individualized therapeutic approach is compulsory [6]. There is considerable and persistent recovery in the metabolic complications related with obesity associated with 5.0 - 10.0% weight reduction [3 - 5]. However, in the Action for Health in Diabetes (Look AHEAD) study showed that 05.0% weight loss did not reduce cardiovascular events, however, 10.0% weight loss was sufficient to achieve reduction in cardiovascular events [7]. Weight loss of more than 07.0% could help patients to achieve remission of T2D and prevent patients with pre-diabetes from progressing further [8]. In the Look AHEAD study emphasized the valuable effects of weight reduction in obese patients with diabetes, demonstrated that a loss of 05.0 - 10.0% of the bodyweight could improve the whole physical fitness, improve glycemic control, and reduce CVS risk and diminution the use of anti-hyperglycemic drugs, antihypertensive drugs and lipid-lowering drugs after one year [9]. The diminution of depression symptoms and the severity of obstructive sleep apnea symptoms [10, 11].

The glucagon-like peptide-1 receptor agonists (GLP-1RAs) are effective at reducing the bodyweight, improving the blood pressure, also having a low risk of hypoglycemia. GLP-1RAs are approved for weight management as an adjunct to diet and exercise in adults with BMI of obese or adults with BMI of overweight who have at least one weight-related condition such as hypertension, T2M and dyslipidemia [12]. GLP-1 is incretin and satiety hormone released from the L-cells of the gastrointestinal tract after food ingestion, liraglutide is GLP-1 analogue with 97.0% structural homology to human native GLP-1, in contrast with endogenous GLP-1 which has half-life of 1 - 2 min. The molecule has two structural modifications allowing it to have prolonged half-life of 13 hrs after subcutaneous injection [13], and there is no hepatic or renal dosing adjustments are necessary with liraglutide [14]. In 2021 ADA guideline, it was announced that GLP-1RAs are preferred first injectable agent for T2D (before insulin therapy) because of their high efficacy and safety [15]. Once-

daily subcutaneous administration of liraglutide and once-weekly dulaglutide therapy were approved as anti-diabetic medications [16]. Thus, higher doses of both have been developed for the treatment of obesity and glucose control in people with or without T2D [17, 18]. Liraglutide has firstly been standard for the treatment of DM, and some studies have then been conducted to evaluate it as therapy for obesity [1], liraglutide dose of 1.8 mg as indicated for T2D and the dose of 3.0 mg indicated for the treatment of obesity [19]. Therefore, this study was aimed to recognize the outcomes from the use of GLP-1RAs on the bodyweight and glycemic response in obese patients with T2D in Libya.

Materials and methods

This prospective cohort study included obese Libyan adults with T2D who have newly been prescribed GLP-1RA therapy with dulaglutide once weekly or liraglutide once daily for six months between July 2013 and May 2022 in Tripoli, at National Diabetic Center. Primary outcomes have been change in body weight, reduction in HbA1c for the study population. An assessment of each patient with help of certified dieticians to give them ideal nutrient advice and exercise encouragement to reduce their bodyweight, regular follow up with diabetologists to adjust their basic anti-hyperglycaemic drugs especially insulin and sulphonyurea doses. The participants were divided randomly into two groups, the first group included 110 patients who received liraglutide pens, and the second group involved 60 patients for dulaglutide pens once weekly. This study was done after having an ethical approval from the Bioethics Committee at the Biotechnology Research Center, Tripoli (number 100/707) dated on November 03rd, 2022.

Statistical analysis: Data of continuous variables were expressed as mean \pm standard deviation. A Chi-square test was used to calculate the difference with 95.0% confidence intervals (95.0% CI) and a $p < 0.05$ was considered as a statistically significant. The analysis was performed with Statistical v10.0 Package (StatSoft, Tulsa, OK, USA).

Results

This study included 170 obese Libyan patients at the National Diabetes Centre with uncontrolled diabetes who started on GLP-1RA as add on therapy to their treatment. Their mean age was 54.1 ± 14.6 years, age interval from ≤ 32 years were in 3 (01.76%) and 43 (25.29%) were between 33 and 53 years old, age period from 54 to 74 years were in 99 (58.23%) and 25 (14.7%) above 75 years and 101 of whom were female patients (59.4%), with a mean duration of DM of 08.8 ± 7.3 years. BMI was calculated for each patient which shown as obesity class I (BMI $> 30.0\%$) in 82 (48.2%), patients with obesity class II (BMI $> 35.0\%$) in 88 (51.7%) and were 83 (48.2%) with HbA1c within 8.0 - 9.0% and 87 (51.8%) with HbA1c $> 10.0\%$, there also were 105 (61.7%) of the patients presented with recurrent hypoglycaemia. They are random distributed into two groups: the first group, 110 patients, received liraglutide once daily injection and were followed for six months (24 weeks) starting dose were 0.6 for one week than increase dose to 1.2 for the next two weeks thereafter to 1.8 for the next 21 weeks (**Table 1**), there basal anti-hyperglycaemic agent reduced according to the self-monitoring blood glucose, liraglutide using group results showed a significant reduction of HbA1c from 9.6% (± 1.54) to 7.4% (± 1.03), $p < 0.001$, and a significant body weight loss from 88.3 kg (± 10.68) to 80.8 kg (± 11.83), $p < 0.001$. The reported adverse events were in 23 cases of minor hypoglycemia due to the gastrointestinal upsets (**Table 1**).

In **Table 2**, the other group included 60 patients for dulaglutide pens taken, the results showed a significant reduction of HbA1c from 9.6% (± 1.54) to 7.1% (± 1.2), $p < 0.05$, and a significant bodyweight loss from 88.3 kg (± 10.68) to 83.8 kg (± 16.3), $p < 0.05$. The reported adverse events were found to be mild transient gastrointestinal distressed for the initial week of start than subside with a regular intake. 115 patients were with HbA1c above 10.0% before start therapy (67.6%), no patient with HbA1c above 10.0% after six months of both GLP-1RA agents therapy were observed in these patients.

Table 1: Body mass index, HbA1c and hypoglycaemic episodes after liraglutide use in obese diabetic patients

Characters Before and after	Before liraglutide use: Initial No.	After six months: End of study No.
<u>Body mass index</u>		
Normal	00.0	30 (27.2%)
Over-weight	00.0	58 (52.8%)
Obesity class 1	53 (48.0%)	22 (20.0%)
Obesity class 2	57 (52.0%)	00.0
<u>HbA1c</u>		
< 6	00.0	63 (57.0%)
6.5 - 7	00.0	37 (34.0%)
8 - 9	36 (33.0%)	10 (09.0%)
> 10	74 (67.0%)	00.0
Hypoglycaemics episodes	48 (44.0%)	23 (20.0%, minor event)

Table 2: Body mass index and HbA1c levels, hypoglycaemic episodes after the use of dulaglutide in obese diabetic patients

Characters Before and after	Before dulaglutide use	After six month
<u>Body mass index</u>		
Normal	00.0	11 (18.0%)
Over-weight	00.0	45 (75.0%)
Obesity class 1	29 (48.0%)	04 (07.0%)
Obesity class 2	31 (52.0%)	00.0
<u>HbA1c</u>		
< 6	00.0	03 (05.0%)
6.5 - 7	00.0	13 (22.0%)
8 - 9	19 (33.0%)	44 (73.0%)
> 10	41 (67.0%)	00.0
Hypoglycaemics episodes	24 (40.0%)	00.0

Discussion

Recently, the rate of coexist cardiovascular risk factors such as hypertension and obesity in Libyan patients with DM is reported by the author [20]. This prospective study aimed to assess the effect of GLP-1RA drugs on the bodyweight and the glycemic control, as well as, the incident of hypoglycemia in obese patients with uncontrolled T2D. In the Satiety and Clinical Adiposity-Liraglutide Evidence in diabetic, individuals (SCALE), obesity and pre-diabetes trials which involved 846 participants with overweight or

obesity showed that liraglutide attained superior to placebo, within the 56 weeks [17]. In our study, the use of liraglutide for 24 weeks as add on therapy resulted on a profound significant bodyweight loss. Liraglutide was superior to placebo in improving glycemic control and reducing cardiovascular events in patients with T2D and high cardiovascular risk in LEADER trial [21] which is in good agreement with the present study. Thus, there was a highly significant improvement in the glycaemic control with a less hypoglycemia response. Similar findings have also been reported [22] in obese patients with T2D followed for one year reported significant difference in HbA1c from 8.9% (± 1.3) to 7.4% (± 1.2) and a significant difference in weight reduction from 98.9 kg (± 16.0) to 93.8 kg (± 15.0) with adverse events in 32 patients mostly as diarrhea (n = 11), nausea (n = 14) and others (n = 7). It was found that after start liraglutide as add on therapy, a highly significant improvement in the glycaemic control with a less hypoglycaemia and highly significant reduction in the bodyweight were observed. A consistent with the systematic literature review by Ostawal and others [23] who reported changes in HbA1c from baseline to study end and found the mean HbA1c change from baseline was - 0.6% to - 2.26%. The mean change in weight from - 1.3 to - 8.65 kg and reported data on adverse effects showing rates ranging from 00.0% to 64.3%. The gastrointestinal effects were most commonly reported with rates of 0.51% to 42.9%. On the other hand, the use of dulaglutide induced a significant improvement in the glycaemic control with a significant reduction in the bodyweight and in the adverse events mild transient gastrointestinal distressed for the initial week of the initiating therapy than subside with regular intake. In fact, a similar finding has previously been reported [24]. In AWARD studies, a large cohort study of T2D patients that dulaglutide provides an effective glucose lowering together with the sustained weight loss and the low incidence of hypoglycemia. However, the current study has some limitations including the small size sample and only one single-center study. Patients were also not followed for the long period to deduce outcome data and link with baseline findings, as the availability of GLP-1RA agents is not continued in the pharmacies.

Conclusion: Use of GLP-1RAs in obese patients with uncontrolled hyperglycemia indicates a profound improvement in the glycemic control and reduce insulin requirement for the blood glucose control with liraglutide. In addition, weight reduction

and less hypoglycemic risk, in particular, with dulaglutide use. The administration of GLP-1RA is best option in obese patients with diabetes with frequent monitoring to adjust basal glucose lowering drugs especially insulin and sulphonylureas doses.

Acknowledgments: The author thanks all the patients who participated in this study and grateful to all the clinic dieticians & nurses for their support during the conduct of the research.

Conflict of interest: The author declares absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

Ethical issues: Including plagiarism, informed consent, data fabrication or falsification and double publication or submission have completely been observed by author.

Data availability statement: The raw data that support the findings of this article are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Author declarations: The author confirms that all relevant ethical guidelines have been followed and any necessary IRB and/or ethics committee approvals have been obtained.

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